
PRINCIPALS' QUALITY CONTROL MEASURES FOR EFFECTIVE TEACHERS' JOB PERFORMANCE IN OGOJA EDUCATIONAL ZONE OF CROSS RIVER STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study investigated principals' quality control measures for effective teachers' job performance in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria. Four research questions guided the study and four null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 2,006 respondents made up of 91 principals and 1,915 teachers in the 91 public secondary schools in Ogoja Education Zone. The sample for this study consisted of 429 respondents (46 principals and 383 teachers) drawn using proportionate stratified sampling technique. A structured questionnaire titled "Principals' Quality Control Measures for Effective Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (PQCMETJPO)" was used for data collection. The instrument was validated by three experts, two from the Department of Educational Management and Planning, and one from Test and Measurement Department, all from Federal College of Education, Obudu. Cronbach alpha was used for a test of internal consistency of the instrument which yielded overall coefficient of 0.79. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and t-test to test the hypotheses. The findings of the study revealed among others that principals apply strategic planning and instructional supervision measures for effective teachers' job performance in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria. It was also found out that principals do not apply performance appraisal and professional development measures for effective teachers' job performance in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that principals should establish quality control units in secondary schools to engage in staff performance appraisal and professional development for effective teachers' job performance.

Keywords: Principals, Quality, Control Measures, Teachers, Job Performance

Introduction

Education is a major driver of economic development through training and producing skilled manpower to engage in productive activities in the society. It is the instrument for developing potentials, inculcating value and shaping the behaviour of individuals to enable them behave responsibly in the society. Ngurukwem, Adebola and Ugwoegbu (2024) opined that education is a crucial tool for equipping individuals with skills and knowledge to make them self-reliant and actively participate in the development of the society. One of level of formal learning institutions that for unlocking the potentials of students and prepare them for productive live is secondary education.

Secondary education takes place after basic level of education to equip students with additional knowledge and skills to prepare them for work life and further studies at higher institutions of learning. Adizibemma and Afangideh (2024) pointed out that secondary education is the phase in education that is responsible for the development potentials and skills of the adolescents. Secondary education offers learning opportunities that enable students to develop critical thinking skills, acquire knowledge of their career interest and advance their competencies to contribute positively to the development of the society. Obona and Sampson (2021) noted that secondary education is designed to prepare students for adulthood by making sure that they learn and equip with the needed skills to become productive workers and full participants in their societies. The daily activities of a secondary school are managed by the principal.

Principal is the chief administrator who plans, organizes and gives directive to ensure smooth running of the daily activities of a secondary school. According to Mbon and Offem (2024), principal is the chief executive officer who carries out leadership responsibilities by coordinating curricular, co-curricular activities and engages in general administration of a secondary school. Principal is the administrator vested with the authority to control the daily operations of a secondary school. Arinze, Egboka and Nwosu (2024) described a principal as the administrator who leads, guides and directs the efforts of others toward the attainment of predetermined goals. They added that principal is responsible for getting work done through scheduling, assigning, motivating and overseeing tasks carried out by members of staff in a secondary school. Principal is the administrative head who plan, direct and control the daily activities of a secondary school. It is the duty of the principal as the administrator to ensure work activities are effectively carried out through quality control measures.

Quality control measures is the strategies for ensuring execution of tasks conform to a specific degree of standards in an organization. Quality control measures is defined by Ogbo, Anyanwu, Emengini, Okeke-James and Umeozor (2021) as the mechanisms put in place to ensure staff diligently carry out their responsibilities in the work. Quality control measures are techniques to ensure conformity to the plan, and standard procedures of operations in learning institutions. According to Adikwu (2021), quality control measures are mechanisms of administrators to meet the expectation of students and personnel in relation to services rendered in educational institutions. Quality control measures are the approaches to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of members of staff in educational institutions. Contextually, quality control measures are mechanisms and procedures to assist and support teachers to ensure that their work activities conform to standard practices for attainment of predetermined educational objectives.

There are varieties of quality control measures that could be applied by principals in running affairs of secondary schools. Eton, Kajang and Omorobi (2020) identified quality control measures to include instructional supervision and staff performance appraisal. Nnadi, Akawnonu, and Okafor (2018) identified strategic planning and inspection as quality control measures in secondary schools. Mbon (2019) listed quality control measures to include staff professional development and resource accountability. The focus of this study is on quality control measures of strategic planning, instructional supervision, performance appraisal and professional development.

Strategic planning is the act of developing visions, deciding programmes, mapping out strategies and marshalling the available resources to attain set goals. Nwafor and Egboka (2020) noted that strategic planning addresses who, where, when and how of reaching desired goals and objectives. Strategic planning measures are strategies for developing blueprint that provide clear directions and serve as a guide to teachers in carrying out their duties in secondary schools. It is through strategic planning that the organization is able to identify the desired outcomes and formulate strategies to achieve them. Strategic planning measures are strategies for deciding activities of schools to attain desired outcomes. It is through strategic planning measures that principals could identify tasks to execute by teachers, decide who, how and when they are to be carried out to achieve set goals. Anukaenyi and Ene (2024) pointed out that strategic planning measures are processes which comprise definition of the goals, a valuation of the resources available for meeting the goals and developing strategies that are intended to achieve the goals. Strategic planning could enable principals to decide when and how to engage in instructional supervision in the classroom.

Instructional supervision is the act of overseeing, directing and guiding the work activities of teachers to enable them effectively carry out their teaching responsibilities in classroom. Instructional supervision is described by Obi, Okekeocha and Gilbert (2024) as the act of overseeing the activities of teachers to render professional guidance and assistance for improving the teaching and learning process. It is instructional supervision measures that principals could ensure standard are maintained in classroom activities. Tarimo and Lekule (2024) noted that principals apply instructional supervision measures through engaging in regular classroom visits to assess, guide, support and offer valuable feedback to teachers for enhancing their effectiveness of teaching methodologies. Also, Onuorah, Uzukwu and Mbonu (2022) noted that principals could supervise teachers based on the schemes of work, specific objectives of the lesson notes, lesson plan, class attendance, absenteeism and levels of hard work, set induction, class control, students' involvement in the lesson, class work, projects and class exercise, teachers conduct and dressing among others. The principals could apply instructional supervision measures to direct and encourage teachers to work hard for attaining desirable results. The observation of principals during supervision could form the basis for performance appraisal.

Staff performance appraisal is a systematic evaluation of work activities carried out by teachers at a given time. Asuquo and Akpadiaha (2022) described performance appraisal measures as systematic processes of planning work, setting expectations, continually monitoring of activities, periodically rating performance in a summary fashion and provision of constructive feedback. Performance appraisal measures for the techniques for conducting periodic review of responsibilities discharged by members of teaching staff. It helps in identifying the strengths and weakness of tasks executed by teachers which forms the basis for guiding and supporting them to

improve on the ways of carried out their job. Wanda, Bisaso, Madinah and Musa (2024) opined that the results of the job performance appraisals are used to determine which employees are performing at the highest level and should receive the bulk of merit-based pay raises, bonuses, and promotions. Additionally, the authors stressed that outcomes of appraisals are utilized to determine whether underachievers require demotion, dismissal or professional development.

Professional development measures are activities geared towards enriching knowledge, competencies and attitudes of teachers to enable them effectively discharge their duties. Professional development measures include to encourage staff to attend accredited corresponding courses, workshops seminars and conferences. Enuah, Amaefule, Nwogbo and Ugwuama (2023) maintained that various professional development measures include: symposiums, continuous training and retention programmes, workshops, research opportunities, conferences and study leave for refresher courses. It involves coaching, mentoring and engaging teachers in job rotation to broaden their knowledge. Ifenaiké, Ore, Hassan and Akporuovo (2021) asserted that in this technological era, teachers need to be regularly and adequately trained and developed in order to be kept abreast of latest development for them to be able to handle the digitally enlightened students. Furthermore, Ifenaiké pointed out that staff development programme is designed for the purpose of improving teachers' skills, promote job effective, improve efficiency and establish future goals for career growth. Staff professional development measures provide platforms for knowledge sharing that help teachers to stay updated with innovative teaching strategies to help to contribute to effective job performance.

Effective teachers' job performance is the and acceptance and timely accomplishment of assigned instructional tasks at a given period. Egboka and Nwosu (2024) described effective teachers' job performance is the ability of a teacher to combine relevant inputs for enhancement of teaching and learning processes. Effective teachers' job performance is positive outcome of the activities carried out by members of teaching staff at a given time in secondary schools. Ike, Alegu and Aso (2022) described effective teachers' job performance as the act, process or manner of executing teaching functions by the teacher either through discipline, teaching instruction, punctuality in class and so on, which impact positively on the students and help in achieving the instructional or educational objective of the educational system. Continuing, Ike et al stressed that it is the ability of teachers to prepare the students under their care to restore glamour and orientation which is affecting the attainment of National aims of education. Contextually, effective teachers' job performance is the devotion of members of teaching staff to their official responsibilities for attainment of desired results at a given time.

Effective job performance is exhibited by teachers who are committed, dedicated and productive. Uduma, Nwifuru and Onu-Robert (2024) asserted that effective teachers' job performance could be measured through annual report of his/ her activities in terms of performance in teaching, lesson preparation, and lesson presentation, mastery of subject matter, commitment to job, extra-curricular activities, class control, supervision and discipline of students' work. Also, Edo and Johnson (2024) noted that the indices of effective teachers' job performance to include regular and early reporting at school, adequate teaching preparation, competence in the subject, adequate lesson presentation, effective supervision of students, participation in extracurricular activities, acting as in loco parentis to students and disciplinary ability among others. Effective teachers' job performance is reflected on their punctuality to work, regularity in classroom to deliver instruction, lesson note preparation, mastery of subject

matter, use of appropriate teaching methods, classroom management, coverage of scheme of work, participation in running daily activities of schools and students' academic achievement among others.

The job performance of teachers seems to be below expectations in public secondary schools in Ogoja Education Zone, Rivers State, Nigeria. Difoni, Obi and Obona (2024) observed laxities in teachers' job performance as some of them often struggle with curriculum coverage, frequently arrive late, and sometimes skip work without permission, exhibit unauthorized absences, failure to mark and correct students' work, lack of use of instructional materials, poor explanation of complex concepts, and inadequate classroom management in public secondary schools in Cross River State. Furthermore, the authors stressed that these shortcomings negatively affect students, leading to a lack of seriousness, tardiness, failure to complete homework, and even involvement in cultism, which ultimately results in poor exam performance. Similarly, Arop, Owan and Ibor (2019) noted that some teachers have been found to be ineffective in their job performance as displayed in their poor attitude to work, poor record keeping habit, not punctuality to school, irregular attendance in classes, giving off notes to students, not marking the attendance register regularly and several other unacceptable behaviors which cannot contribute to the attainment of set goals and objectives of the school system in Cross River State. In the same vein, Abam, Amos and Igwebuikwe (2024) asserted that some teachers do not report to duty as expected, display unfavorable attitude, fail to prepare lesson notes and demonstrating a high degree of absenteeism in public secondary schools in Cross Rivers State, Nigeria.

The laxities in teachers' job performance could perhaps cause by inadequate measures put in place by principals to control their activities in public secondary schools in Cross Rivers State, Nigeria. Egbeji (2023) noted that the quality of teacher is still low, both in terms of competence, knowledge, and pedagogical expertise due to a large extent to the poor management of the teacher performance system in public secondary schools in Cross River State, Nigeria. The author added that supervision in has been reduced to witch-hunting and corrupt practices such as extorting money from teachers in public secondary schools, Cross River State. It appears that there is insufficient plan to support teachers in discharging their duties. Teachers tend to be rarely supervised and retrained to update their skills and knowledge in public secondary schools in Cross Rivers State, Nigeria. To buttress this, Chuktu and Uzoigwe (2019) maintained that there seems to be a poor implementation of induction, in-service training and other capacity building programmes which tend to make some teachers use obsolete skills in the course carrying out their responsibilities and thereby contribute to their low productivity in public secondary schools in Cross Rivers State, Nigeria. Marchie and Ntuno (2024) noted that the absence of regular in-service training and sponsorship of conferences by school administrators and Ministry of Education for the professional development of teachers in public secondary schools in Cross River State. Undeniably, the authors added that without professional development in schools, teachers will be stock with old method of teaching, lack new teaching strategies; thereby making teaching boring and unsatisfactory, resulting to poor performance and unproductivity in general school system. Tawo and Nwachuya (2023) observed that the poor performance of students witnessed in public education, high rate of examination, unprecedented level of school dropout and low intake of admission to tertiary institutions could be partly due to irregular strategic supervision of teachers' instructions in public secondary schools in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria. It is against this background that the study

investigated principals' quality control measures for effective teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Principals by the virtue of their position have the responsibilities of ensuring the work activities of teachers meet minimum acceptable standard of educational practices through quality control measures of strategic planning, instructional supervision, performance appraisal and staff professional development. It is worrisome that some principals tend to make plan that fail to address the needs and priorities of public secondary schools in Cross River State, Nigeria. The work activities of teachers tend to be irregularly reviewed by principals to determine how well they perform their job in the classroom. Some teachers teach with outdated skills and knowledge probably due to they are denied the opportunities to participate in training programmes. It seems that some principals neglect their supervision roles by falling to oversee the activities of teachers and offer the needed supports to effectively discharge their duties. This tend to contribute to the laxities in the job performance of some teachers in public secondary schools in Cross River State, Nigeria.

Sone of laxities in job performance of some teachers appear to be shown through persistent absenteeism, arriving late to work, unnecessary movement from duty, fail to teach students in the classroom and cover their scheme of work among others in public secondary schools in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria. It seems that there are some teachers that teach with outdated lesson note, fail to mark attendance register of students and exhibit other forms of professional misconduct in public secondary schools in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria. Consequently, students receive low quality of education, engage in examination malpractices and perform poorly in examinations. The persistent of low quality of education appears to adversely affect the students' acquisition of the necessary skills needed by them to develop their potential and enhance the development of Cross Rivers State. It is the light of these problems that an investigation was carried out into principals' quality control measures for effective teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to determine principals' quality control measures for effective teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Investigate principals' strategic planning measures for effective teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria.
2. Find out principals' instructional supervision measures for effective teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria.
3. Determine principals' performance appraisal measures for effective teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria.
4. Examine principals' professional development measures for effective teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the principals' strategic planning measures for effective teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria?
2. What are the principals' instructional supervision measures for effective teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria?
3. What are the principals' performance appraisal measures for effective teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria?
4. What are the principals' professional development measures for effective teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on principals' strategic planning measures for effective teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on principals' instructional supervision measures for effective teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on principals' performance appraisal measures for effective teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria.
4. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on principals' professional development measures for effective teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 2,006 respondents made up of 91 principals and 1,915 teachers in the 91 public secondary schools in Ogoja Education Zone. The sample for this study was 429 respondents made up of 46 principals and 383 teachers drawn using proportionate stratified random sampling technique. A-researcher developed instrument titled "Principals' Quality Control Measures for Effective Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (PQCMETJPQ)" was used for data collection. The instrument was developed by the researchers from literature review and consultation with experts in the field. PQCMETJPQ has sections A and B. Section A was structured to elicit information on bio data of respondents. Section B has four clusters namely: I, II III and IV. These clusters were based on the four areas of quality control measures covered in the study. Cluster 1 had seven items on strategic planning measures; cluster II contained eight

items on instructional supervision measures; Cluster III had seven items on performance appraisal measures and cluster IV contained eight items on professional development measures. The instrument therefore contains a total of 30 items all of which are structured on a four-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D); Strongly Disagree (SD) weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively.

The instrument was subjected to face validation by three experts, two from the Department of Educational Management and Planning, and one from Test and Measurement Department, all from Federal College of Education, Obudu. The experts were requested to examine and scrutinize the items in terms of content, relevance, suitability, clarity and coverage of the dimensions of the study. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach's alpha which yielded reliability coefficient values of 0.81, 0.79, 0.77 and 0.77 for Cluster I to IV respectively with an overall coefficient value of 0.79 which indicates that the instruments are reliable.

The instrument was administered by the researchers with the help of three research assistants who are secondary school teachers in Ogoja Education Zone. A total of 429 copies of the questionnaire were distributed, 46copies to principals and 383 copies to teachers. Out of these, a total of 417 copies of questionnaire of which 46 copies were from principals and 371 copies were from teachers were properly filled and successfully retrieved, indicating 97% percent return. At the end of the exercise, duly completed and retrieved copies of the questionnaire were used for data analysis. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and t-test to test the hypotheses. In taking decisions on the research questions, mean rating of 2.50 or above was taken as agreement, while any mean rating of below 2.50 indicate disagreement. The decision criteria for the null hypotheses is that if p-value is equal to or greater than significant value of 0.05, the null hypothesis was accepted, but if p-value is less than significant value of 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: What are the principals' strategic planning measures for effective teachers' job performance in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation Scores on Principals' Strategic Planning Measures for Effective Teachers' Job Performance

S/N	ITEMS	Principals (n = 46)			Teachers (n =371)		
		\bar{x}	SD	Remark	\bar{x}	SD	Remark
1	Develop mission to help teachers remain focus on the track of attaining set goals in school	2.65	1.10	Agree	2.57	1.03	Agree
2	Formulate guidelines for operation to prevent teachers from detecting standard in their instructional delivery	2.45	1.05	Disagree	2.41	1.09	Disagree
3	Give priorities to the needs of teachers to boost their morale in doing their job	2.52	1.07	Agree	2.48	1.04	Disagree
4	Plan empowerment programmes to improve the efficiency of teachers	2.74	1.03	Agree	2.87	1.06	Agree

5	Schedule the work activities in convent ways to motivate them in carrying out their duties	2.69	1.11	Agree	2.78	1.01	Agree
6	Map out strategies to give direction to teachers for improving teaching and learning activities	2.72	1.09	Agree	2.77	0.98	Agree
7	Set targets for teachers to prevent distractions in doing their job	2.56	0.98	Agree	2.54	1.07	Agree
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation		2.62	1.06	Agree	2.63	1.03	Agree

As in Table 1, the mean ratings of both principals and teachers for items 1, 4, 5, 6 and 7 are above the cut off mean of 2.50 indicating agreement with the items as principals' strategic planning measures for effective teachers' job performance. The principals and teachers mean ratings for item 2 is below the cut off mean score of 2.50 indicating their disagreement with the items as principals' strategic planning measures for effective teachers' job performance. The mean score of 2.52 obtained by principals for item 3 which is above 2.50 indicated agreement, while that of teachers which is 2.48 indicated disagreement with the item. The standard deviation scores of 1.06 and 1.03 for principals and teachers respectively indicates that there is homogeneity amongst their responses. The cluster mean of 2.62 and 2.63 for principals and teachers respectively which is above 2.50 indicated that principals apply strategic planning measures for effective teachers' job performance in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria.

Research Question 2: What are the principals' instructional supervision measures for effective teachers' job performance in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation Scores on Principals' Instructional Supervision Measures for Effective Teachers' Job Performance

S/N	ITEMS	Principals (n = 46)			Teachers (n =371)		
		\bar{x}	SD	Remark	\bar{x}	SD	Remark
8	Pay unscheduled visit to teachers in the classroom to observe their instructional activities and make suggestions for improvement	2.71	0.97	Agree	2.84	1.07	Agree
9	Inspect school daily attendance record of teachers to ensure their regularity in school for discharging duties	2.46	1.02	Disagree	2.48	1.11	Disagree
10	Check lesson plan prepared by teachers to guide them on areas that need modifications	2.57	1.03	Agree	2.60	1.09	Agree
11	Inspect the lesson notes of teachers to ensure that they are well prepared	2.69	1.00	Agree	2.61	1.05	Agree
12	Vet the objectives of lessons set by teachers to direct them on ways to improve on it.	2.58	1.03	Agree	2.62	1.04	Agree
13	Monitor the class control of teachers to assist them in managing the behaviour	2.69	1.03	Agree	2.71	1.08	Agree

	of students						
14	Observe teachers' display of the knowledge of their subject matters to offer suggestions for improvement.	2.70	1.01	Agree	2.61	1.04	Agree
15	Check the clarity of the voices of teachers during instructional delivery	2.85	1.05	Agree	2.59	1.02	Agree
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation		2.66	1.02	Agree	2.63	1.06	Agree

Table 2 revealed that all the items except item 9 have mean ratings above the cut off mean score of 2.50 in respect to both the principals and the teachers' responses indicating agreement with the statements as principals' instructional supervision measures for effective teachers' job performance. The pooled standard deviation scores which stood at 1.02 and 1.06 for principals and teachers respectively indicated that their responses are close to the mean, implying that the respondents are homogenous in their responses amongst cluster. The cluster mean of 2.66 and 2.63 for principals and teachers respectively which are above 2.50 indicated agreement that principals apply instructional supervision measures for effective teachers' job performance in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria

Research Question 3: What are the principals' performance appraisal measures for effective teachers' job performance in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria?

Table 3: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation Scores on Principals' Performance Appraisal Measures for Effective Teachers' Job Performance

S/N	ITEMS	Principals (n = 46)			Teachers (n =371)		
		\bar{x}	SD	Remark	\bar{x}	SD	Remark
16	Engage in periodic assessment of teachers' knowledge of curriculum contents	2.48	1.02	Disagree	2.44	1.10	Disagree
17	Carry out periodic evaluation of the general work attitude of teachers to offer guidance	2.52	1.01	Agree	2.51	1.09	Agree
18	Compare the actual results of work done by teachers with the expected ones	2.47	1.04	Disagree	2.42	1.06	Disagree
19	Review the scheme of work covered by teachers in a given term	2.55	1.03	Agree	2.53	1.09	Agree
20	Review profession conduct of teachers to offer counselling services to those that need it	2.45	0.98	Disagree	2.48	1.05	Disagree
21	Set corrective steps to overcome deficiencies in the job performance of teachers	2.41	0.97	Disagree	2.37	1.04	Disagree
22	Provide honest feedback on tasks executed by staff	2.50	1.08	Agree	2.49	1.07	Disagree
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation		2.48	1.02	Disagree	2.46	1.07	Disagree

The result in table 3 shows that principals and teachers recorded mean scores of below 2.50 for items 16, 18, 20 and 21 indicating disagreement with the items as the principals' performance

appraisal measures for effective teachers' job performance. The mean ratings of principals and teachers for items 17 and 19 are above 2.50 indicating disagreement with the statements as principals' performance appraisal measures for effective teachers' job performance. The mean scores of 2.50 recorded by principals for item 22 is above 2.50 showing with agreement as parts of principals' performance appraisal measures for effective teachers' job performance, while teachers recorded mean score of 2.46 which is below 2.50 indicates disagreement with the item.

The pooled standard deviation scores of 1.02 for principals and 1.07 for teachers respectively showed that closer convergence of the mean ratings. The cluster means of 2.48 for principals and 2.46 for teacher are below 2.50 indicating that the principals do not apply performance appraisal measures for effective teachers' job performance in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria.

Research Question 4: What are the principals' professional development measures for effective teachers' job performance in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria?

Table 4: Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation Scores on Principals' Professional Development Measures for Effective Teachers' Job Performance

S/N	ITEMS	Principals (n = 46)			Teachers (n =371)		
		\bar{x}	SD	Remark	\bar{x}	SD	Remark
23	Teachers are encouraged to attend to seminars to enrich the knowledge of their subject matters	2.46	1.10	Disagree	2.44	1.06	Disagree
24	Workshops are organized for teachers to enable them have practical experience of solving classroom problems	2.53	1.01	Agree	2.51	1.07	Agree
25	Funds are set aside to sponsor conferences of teachers to improve their teaching skills	2.35	1.10	Disagree	2.30	1.01	Disagree
26	Induction courses are organized for teachers to get conversant innovative teaching methods	2.54	1.03	Agree	2.55	1.02	Agree
27	Teachers are supported to enrol in short professional courses to keep abreast of latest trends in teaching	2.43	0.96	Disagree	2.39	1.11	Disagree
28	Symposiums are organised for teachers to share experiences that can improve the ways of carrying out their duties	2.52	1.00	Agree	2.50	1.03	Agree
29	Teachers are sponsored to refresher courses to improve their knowledge of carrying out instructional activities	2.41	1.04	Disagree	2.45	1.01	Disagree
30	Teachers are encouraged to enrol in distance programmes up-date their instructional strategies	2.46	1.08	Disagree	2.44	0.99	Disagree
Cluster Mean and Standard Deviation		2.46	1.04	Disagree	2.45	1.04	Disagree

Table 4 shows that the mean ratings of principals and teachers for items 23, 25, 27, 29 and 30 which are below 2.50 indicating disagreement with the items as parts of principals' professional development measures for effective teachers' job performance. On the other hand, mean ratings of principals and teachers for items 24, 26 and 28 which are above 2.50 indicating disagreement with the items as parts of principals' professional development measures for effective teachers' job performance. The pooled standard deviation scores of 1.04 for principals and 1.04 for teachers respectively showed that their mean ratings are fairly cluster. Both principals and teachers have cluster mean of 2.46 and 2.45 respectively which are below 2.50 revealed that principals do not apply professional development measures for effective teachers' job performance in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on principals' strategic planning measures for effective teachers' job performance in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria.

Table 5: The t-test Summary of Mean Ratings of Principals and Teachers on Principals' Strategic Planning Measures for Effective Teachers' Job Performance

Respondents	N	\bar{x}	SD	p-value	Df	Alpha	Remark
Principals	46	2.62	1.06	0.11	415	0.05	Not Significant
Teachers	371	2.63	1.03				

Data presented in table 5 reveals that the p-value of 0.11 is greater than 0.05 alpha level. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on principals' strategic planning measures for effective teachers' job performance in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on principals' instructional supervision measures for effective teachers' job performance in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria.

Table 6: The t-test Summary of Mean Ratings of Principals and Teachers on Principals' Instructional Supervision Measures for Effective Teachers' Job Performance

Respondents	N	\bar{x}	SD	p-value	Df	Alpha	Remark
Principals	46	2.66	1.02	0.01	415	0.05	Not Significant
Teachers	371	2.63	1.06				

Table 6 reveals that the p-value of 0.21 is greater than 0.05 alpha level. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on principals' instructional supervision measures for effective teachers' job performance in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria.

Ho₃: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on principals' performance appraisal measures for effective teachers' job performance in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria.

Table 7: The t-test Summary of Mean Ratings of Principals and Teachers on Principals' Performance Appraisal Measures for Effective Teachers' Job Performance

Respondents	N	\bar{x}	SD	p-value	Df	Alpha	Remark
Principals	46	2.48	1.02	0.16	415	0.05	Not Significant
Teachers	371	2.46	1.07				

As shown in table 7, the p-value of 0.16 is greater than 0.05 alpha level. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on principals' strategic planning measures for effective teachers' job performance in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria.

Ho₄: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on principals' professional development measures for effective teachers' job performance in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria.

Table 8: The t-test Summary of Mean Ratings of Principals and Teachers on Principals' Professional Development Measures for Effective Teachers' Job Performance

Respondents	N	\bar{x}	SD	p-value	Df	Alpha	Remark
Principals	46	2.46	1.04	0.17	415	0.05	Not Significant
Teachers	371	2.45	1.04				

Table 8 shows that the p-value of 0.17 is greater than 0.05 alpha level. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on principals' professional development measures for effective teachers' job performance in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria.

Discussion

The finding of the study revealed that principals' apply strategic planning measures for effective teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria. This agreed with the finding of Nwafor and Egboka (2020) indicated that principals apply strategic planning practices in secondary schools. This is in line with the finding of Ibrahim, Kyando and Kiwonde (2023) which revealed that strategic planning practices are adopted by principals for improving school performance. The similarity in time span could account for the agreement between the findings. This refuted the finding of Gawie and Masese (2016) which showed that strategic planning measures are not applied by principals in secondary schools. The difference in time span of eight years which bring about changes in research findings and this could explain the disagreement. Principals' strategic planning measures for effective teachers' job performance in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria included to develop mission to help teachers remain focus on the track of attaining set goals in school, plan empowerment programmes to improve the efficiency of teachers, schedule the work activities in convenient ways to motivate them in carrying out their duties, map out strategies to give direction to teachers for improving teaching and learning activities and set targets for teachers to prevent distractions in doing their job. The possible explanation for this finding is that principals strategic planning measures to set goals, organize the efforts of teachers and allocate resources to ensure that they are working towards improving their job performance in secondary schools. It was also found that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and

teachers on principals' strategic planning measures for effective teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria.

The result of the study revealed that principals' apply instructional supervision measures for effective teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria. This is consonance with the finding of Madudili (2021) which showed that instructional supervision is applied by principals to improve teachers' job performance in secondary schools. The agreement between the findings could be attributed to the fact that the two studies were conducted in secondary schools using similar participants. Principals' instructional supervision measures for effective teachers' job performance in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria were to pay unscheduled visit to teachers in the classroom to observe their instructional activities and make suggestions for improvement, check lesson plan prepared by teachers to guide them on areas that need modifications, inspect the lesson notes of teachers to ensure that they are well prepared, vet the objectives of lessons set by teachers to direct them on ways to improve on it, monitor the class control of teachers to assist them in managing the behaviour of students, observe teachers' display of the knowledge of their subject matters to offer suggestions for improvement and check the clarity of the voices of teachers during instructional delivery. Principals probably apply instructional supervision measures to guide and support teachers to improve teaching activities in the classroom. Further result showed that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on principals' instructional supervision measures for effective teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria. This affirmed the finding of Madudili (2021) which indicated that there is no significant difference between mean ratings of principals and teachers on the extent to which they perceived instructional supervision as a tool for improving teachers' performance in secondary schools.

The finding of the study revealed that principals' do not apply performance appraisal measures for effective teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria. This is conformity with the finding of Takiso and Labiso (2019) which revealed that principals do not apply teachers' performance appraisal measures in primary schools. The similarity in the level of education in which the studies were conducted might contribute to the agreement between the findings. The performance appraisal measures that were not applied by principals for effective teachers' job performance in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria included to engage in periodic assessment of teachers' knowledge of curriculum contents, compare the actual results of work done by teachers with the expected ones, review profession conduct of teachers to offer counselling services to those that need it and set corrective steps to overcome deficiencies in the job performance of teachers. Some principals are reluctant to appraise job performance of teachers probably due to insufficient skills and knowledge to evaluate their activities in secondary schools. It was also found that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on principals' performance appraisal measures for effective teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria. This upheld the finding of Unachukwu and Nwanga (2021) which showed that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the staff performance appraisal practices adopted by principals in secondary schools. The similarity in participants of the studies could explain the agreement between the findings.

The result of the study revealed that principals' do not apply professional development measures for effective teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria. This supported the finding of Egboka (2018) which revealed that principals do not apply professional development practices for enhancing teachers' job performance in secondary schools. This is contrary to the finding of Nwankwo and Ilozue (2023) which revealed that staff professional development strategies were applied by principals for teachers' job performance in secondary schools. The difference in geographical location could explain the contradiction between the findings. The professional development measures that were not applied by principals for effective teachers' job performance in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria included that teachers are encouraged to attend to seminars to enrich the knowledge of their subject matters, funds are set aside to sponsor conferences of teachers to improve their teaching skills, teachers are supported to enrol in short professional courses to keep abreast of latest trends in teaching, teachers are sponsored to refresher courses to improve their knowledge of carrying out instructional activities and teachers are encouraged to enrol in distance programmes up-date their instructional strategies. Principals do not apply professional development measures probably due to insufficient funds to organize such programmes for teachers. It was also discovered that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on principals' professional development measures for effective teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria. This is in line with the finding of Egboka and Francis-Okorie (2024) which showed that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of principals and teachers on the professional development practices adopted by principals for improving teachers' job performance in secondary schools. The similarity in time span might be responsible for the agreement between the findings.

Conclusion

Based on the finding of the study, it is concluded that principals' apply some aspect of quality control measures for effective teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria. The aspect of quality control measures applied by principals were strategic planning and instructional supervision, while they failed to apply performance appraisal and professional development measures in public secondary schools in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria. Quality control measures applied by principals play essential roles towards improving the standard of education in public secondary schools in Ogoja Educational Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Principals should attend leadership courses to improve on their strategic planning measures to bring about effective teachers' job performance.
2. Principals should constitute instructional supervision committee to assist in overseeing the work activities of teachers and rendering needed assistance to facilitate effective job performance.
3. Federal Ministry of Education should handbook to guide principals in conducting termly performance appraisal of teachers to enhance their effective job performance.

4. State Secondary Education Board should periodic professional development for teachers to upgrade their skills for enhancing effective job performance.
5. Principals should establish quality control units in secondary schools to engage in staff performance appraisal and professional development for effective teachers' job performance.

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